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Scientific Contributions and Gaps in *Hura crepitans* L. Research: A Comprehensive Bibliometric Analysis of Publications From 1909 to 2024

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Abstract

Hura crepitans, is a species endemic to tropical parts of North and South America, including the Amazon rainforest. It is well-known for its unusual traits, which have important ecological and ethnobotanical applications. Bibliometric analysis was performed using data from Web of Science, Scopus, Research4Life, PubMed, and Google Scholar in May 2024 with “*Hura crepitans*”, “*Hura brasiliensis*”, “*Hura senegalensis*”, and “*Hura strepens*” as keywords. A total of 453 publications were collected, and after eliminating duplicates and irrelevant publications, 194 scientific production all articles were used for the analysis. The temporal evolution of publications and their total citations over time was computed, and content analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and Bibliometrix with Biblioshiny. ArcGIS version 10.4 was used to produce the spatial distribution map and access the spatial pattern of publications. Social network analysis was conducted to understand research networks and clusters using Gephi version 0.9. The results showed a relatively low publication trend during the early decades, with sporadic publications appearing every few years. A significant increase in publications has occurred since 2000. English productions account for 88.14%, with 3,870 citations, averaging 22.63 citations per publication. Forest Ecology and Management emerged as the most productive source, followed by the Journal of Ethnopharmacology. Knowledge gap analysis revealed the need for research to investigate *Hura crepitans* toxicity, secure production methods, and ecological connections outside its native location like other African nations in which it has been introduced for deeply mastering the species’ multiple advantages in medicine, industry, agriculture, and other fields.

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Introduction

Understanding ecological dynamics, biodiversity protection, and possible applications in various industries, including agriculture, medicine, and environmental management, requires a knowledge of plant species. Therefore, plant species from earth's natural ecosystems are suitable candidates for scientists to be particularly interested in. Among them, *Hura crepitans*, commonly known as sandbox tree, possumwood, monkey no-climb in English, and Portuguese as assacu, (Tupi: asaku), and jabillo is a remarkable evergreen tree from the Euphorbiaceae family (Esonu *et al.*, 2014; Issac *et al.*, 2023). It is endemic to tropical parts of North and South America, including the Amazon rainforest (Sidohoude *et al.*, 2019). *Hura crepitans* is well-known for its unusual traits, which have important ecological and ethnobotanical applications. It has several synonyms, including *Hura brasiliensis*, *Hura senegalensis*, *Hura strepens*, and different varieties of *Hura crepitans*. In the wild, it can reach 40 m in height with a stem and main branches densely spiny. The bark is generally grey with black, conical spines (Ajani *et al.*, 2019). Its stipules are lanceolate or ovate-lanceolate 10 to 15 mm long and 2 to 3 mm thick. The leaf has a broadly ovate blade of 5 to 29 cm in length and 5 to 17 cm in width attached to a 4 to 20 cm long petiole. The leaf blade is papery, abaxially pilose along the midrib, and elevated on both surfaces, with 10 to 16 lateral veins on each side (Owojuyigbe *et al.*, 2020). It has a cordate base and caudate-acuminate apex. The margins are more or less shallowly dentate-serrate. The male flowers are ovoid-conical inflorescence, mostly dark red. The female flower is often solitary, with a cup-shaped calyx terminating in a thick apical disc of 1 cm in diameter and 5 to 20 radiating lobes of 5 to 10 mm. The fruiting pedicel is pendent to 6 cm, holding an oblate fruit of 3 to 5 × 8 to 9 cm in diameter, concave at its apex and base, and longitudinally grooved, becoming reddish brown. It contains brownish and smooth seeds 5 to 8 mm thick and 15 to 20 mm in diameter. Perhaps the most unusual feature is the fruit capsule, which, when ripe, explodes with a

rattling sound, distributing its seeds thus the name crepitans, which means "rattling" (Esonu *et al.*, 2014). This extraordinary plant has enormous application potential, necessitating additional research into its chemical composition, ecological roles, and possible uses in medicine, agriculture, and biofuel production (Issac *et al.*, 2023). *Hura crepitans* have unique phytochemical properties that scientists are fascinated by because of their prospective applications in industry and health. Several studies have highlighted its potential for phytochemical screening, nutraceutical potential, and anti-inflammatory effects (Avoseh *et al.*, 2018; Ajani *et al.*, 2019). Despite the increased amount of research, there are still many uncertainties concerning this species, particularly its many applications and ecological services in Africa (Owojuyigbe *et al.*, 2020; Issac *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, little is known about this species in Benin. The only notable studies undertaken in Benin have focused on converting seed oil into biodiesel (Sidohoude *et al.*, 2019).

Bibliometric or bibliometric analysis is a quantitative analysis method that uses mathematical and statistical tools to measure the interrelationships and impacts of publications within a given area of research or on a given subject. It provides a global overview of many academic studies. It is also used to efficiently identify influential studies, authors, journals, organizations, and countries over time and established and emerging research areas (van Eck and Waltman, 2010). Bibliometric analysis has been applied in various disciplines to scale up research performance and assess trends in scientific publications, including authorship, thematic areas, geographical origins, and citation counts (Pritchard, 1969). This approach has also been used to analyze scientific production's spatial and temporal distribution on a group of species or a single species from both the animal and plant kingdoms (Bertin *et al.*, 2018; Duan *et al.*, 2020; Saggiomo *et al.*, 2020). This approach has also been useful in conducting meta-analyses and systematic reviews, particularly for human health and environmental conservation

(Abrahamse and Steg, 2013). Bibliometric analysis is a powerful approach to uncovering and summarizing the existing knowledge on a particular topic and shedding light on the existing gaps for further research endeavors. Although bibliometric analysis has been applied to various species, to our knowledge, it has not yet been applied to *Hura crepitans* to bridge knowledge gaps and expand our understanding of the species' potential, the research areas, and the research aspects worth investigating. Understanding the current level of research on this species is critical for improving our knowledge on this subject and ensuring that future studies are informed and strategically focused (Ajani *et al.*, 2019; Owojuyigbe *et al.*, 2020). In the current work, bibliometric analysis was used to access the spatial and temporal distribution of knowledge on *Hura crepitans* to provide light on the species' research environment by identifying prior scientific endeavors as well as the major gaps that remain to be filled. This study aims to answer the following questions: i) What are the spatial and temporal distributions of knowledge on *Hura crepitans*? ii) How was collaborative research conducted on *Hura crepitans*? iii) What and who are the leading actors in the investigations of *Hura crepitans*? iv) What are the most and least covered aspects of research on *Hura crepitans* worldwide?

Materials and methods

Data collection

Bibliometric analysis mainly uses various platforms or repositories that provide access to scientific productions and/or citation indices. Web of Science and Scopus are the key scientific production databases retrieved from and used to conduct bibliometric analyses. Contrary to these well-known and widely used databases, some others, including Research4Life, PubMed, and Google Scholar, are less used due to various reasons extending from lack of knowledge about their existence to the questionable quality of the scientific productions available on them. Research4Life is an initiative which is a public-private partnership comprising of research institutions and UN agencies. The goal of

Research4Life is to provide affordable access to scholarly, professional, and research information in least developing countries. It is the collective name for five programs *viz.* Research in Health (Hinari), Research in Agriculture (AGORA), Research in the Environment (OARE), Research for Development and Innovation (ARDI), and Research for Global Justice (GOALI) that provide developing countries with free or low-cost access to up to 81,000 leading journals and books in the fields of health, agriculture, environment, and applied sciences. Research4Life also allows access to Web of Science and Scopus databases via its platform. PubMed is a free resource for searching and retrieving biomedical and life sciences literature. It was developed and maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) at the U.S.

National Library of Medicine (NLM), located at the National Institutes of Health (NIH). PubMed database contains more than 36 million citations and abstracts. Google Scholar is a free access web search engine that provides an easy and simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature from many disciplines and sources. By using a web crawler, Google Scholar can find about 100 million scholarly documents written in English on the Web. However, it has been criticized for including predatory journals.

To carry out the current bibliometric analysis and to ensure consideration of almost the comprehensive scientific productions available on *Hura crepitans*, scientific productions were gathered from Scopus, Web of Science, Research4life, PubMed, and Google Scholar in May 2024 using the following keywords "*Hura crepitans*", "*Hura brasiliensis*", "*Hura senegalensis*", and "*Hura strepens*". Given the structure of the various platforms, the keywords were searched in the publication title, keywords, and abstract on Web of Science, Scopus and Research4life. On PubMed, the same keywords were searched in publications' titles and abstracts, while on Google Scholar, they were searched in publications' titles only and by checking the box exclude citations.

Data cleaning and merging

The search performed yielded 159 records from Scopus, 125 from Web of Science, 30 from PubMed, and 115 from Research4Life, leading to 431 documents that were supplemented by 22 additional documents from Google Scholar, totaling 453 documents of various types. These scientific productions collected from these various platforms were scrutinized separately to remove duplicated entries, theses, and reports within the database when they exist. Given the questionable quality of some scientific productions from Google Scholar, all the scientific productions in published predatory journals were removed after checking the journal's name on beallist.net. After this first removal of duplicates and elimination of scientific productions published in predatory journals, the data from the selected platforms were merged and a second removal of duplicates between platforms was conducted. The data from Web of Science and Scopus were prioritized during this process.

This means that when an entry exists in Web of Science and Scopus, the one from Web of Science is kept while the one from Scopus is removed while keeping its citations count information from Scopus. Similarly, when a duplicated entry exists in Scopus, the one from Scopus is kept, and others are removed. The prioritization of the platform continues from Research4Life to PubMed and Google Scholar. Since information on scientific production from Research4Life, PubMed, and Google Scholar lacks some information that is present in data from Web of Science and Scopus, such publications were individually downloaded and used to complement their missing information in the merged database. Since citation counts are provided by both Scopus and Web of Science, the maximum value of citations from the two platforms was used. As in most bibliometric analyses, it is common to exclude all document types different from articles and reviews because they usually are not peer-reviewed and evaluated in their full length (Garza-Reyes, 2015; de Oliveira *et al.*, 2019). Over the 453 documents obtained, 259 documents were removed, and the remaining 194

publications, all articles, were considered for further analysis.

Data analysis

The temporal evolution of publications and their total citations over time was computed, and Microsoft Office Excel 2019 was used to produce the graph and table. The maximum value from the two databases from which publications were retrieved was used for the total citation.

Based on the authors' affiliation, the authors' country information was extracted and used to determine the contribution of countries worldwide in publications on the searched species. Only publications having affiliation information provided were considered, and ArcGIS version 10.4 was used with the world geopolitical boundaries of countries layer retrieved from the geospatial data portal of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, geospatial information for sustainable food systems) to produce the map of the spatial distribution and access the spatial pattern of the publications.

Content analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and Bibliometrix (Version 4.1.4) with Biblioshiny, which is an open-source application based on R used for extensive analysis and mapping of scientific literature. The choice of the Bibliometrix package with built-in Biblioshiny for material is related to its extensibility in the RStudio programming language. Furthermore, the open-source nature provides frequent updates and constant support from a community of users and developers, keeping these tools relevant and viable over time (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017). Additionally, its availability is free compared with other programs that may be pricey or require memberships to access comparable capacity (Güler, 2023). The extensive documentation and learning resources available for these tools facilitate their adoption and effective use, providing researchers with a solid basis for conducting meaningful and accurate bibliometric analyses and enabling information mapping using simple and complex illustrations (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017). Social network analysis was

conducted to understand research networks and clusters using Gephi version 0.9 software. Gephi was chosen given its flexibility to analyze the collaboration network with ease by moving gradually in the degree of complexity and the quality of the graphics it provides. For the social network analysis, we created authors' countries and authors' networks to investigate the level of collaboration between countries, especially amongst African countries and overseas partners, as well as between leading authors. In this analysis, nodes represent authors or countries and edges represent publications on which two authors or countries have collaborated. The strength of the network (edge) relates to the number of publications the two have co-published. As is common in other bibliometric analyses, research published by authors from England, North Ireland, Scotland, and Wales were labeled as documents from

the United Kingdom (Liu *et al.*, 2011; Yevide *et al.*, 2016).

Results

Publication types, citation patterns, and language distribution

The publication trend for *Hura crepitans* shows that the number of publications was relatively low during the early decades (1909-1999), with sporadic publications appearing every few years (Fig. 1). From 2000 to 2012, there was a noticeable increase in research activity, with the number of publications rising consistently and peaking at various points, particularly in the late 2000s and early 2010s. From 2013 onward, there has been a significant and sustained increase in the number of publications, indicating a growing interest and continued research focus on *Hura crepitans* in recent years.

Table 1. Publication language and their impacts.

Languages	Number of publications	Percentage (%)	Total citation	Total citations per publication	Total citations per publication per year
English	171	88.14	3870	22.63	1.51
French	7	3.61	8	1.14	0.03
German	3	1.55	6	2.00	0.06
Portuguese	5	2.58	22	4.40	0.48
Spanish	8	4.12	28	3.50	0.38
Total	194	100	3934	20.28	1.36

The first publication on *Hura crepitans* focuses on isolating a substance known as a haemagglutinating constituent, crepitine (Richet, 1909). This substance is profoundly studied through experiences made by Jaffe and Seidl from 1943 to 1969, who isolated and characterized the substance named Hurain extract from the sap of *Hura crepitans*.

The citation trend for research on *Hura crepitans* shows fluctuations over the years, with notable peaks at certain periods (Fig. 1). Early citations (before 1975) were sporadic and low, reflecting the limited number of publications during that time and also the weak impact of research on the topic. From 1975 onwards, visible peaks in citations indicate periods of increased academic interest and impact. The most significant rise in citations appears around the late 1990s to early 2000s, coinciding with the increased

number of publications. There was a notable citation dip after this peak, but a subsequent rise occurred from 2010 onward, reflecting a renewed and growing interest in *Hura crepitans*.

In the analysis of 194 publications on *Hura crepitans*, English emerged as the most productive language, constituting 88.14% of the total publications (Table 1). These English-language publications received a substantial number of citations, totaling 3,870, with an average of 22.63 citations per publication and an annual citation rate of 1.51. The second most used language was Spanish, which, unlike English, has an average impact close to Portuguese, though this latter recorded fewer publications. In contrast, while French was among the top three most used languages, comprising 3.61% of the total publications, it had the lowest impact in terms of citations.

Table 2. Source of publication on *Hura crepitans*.

Sources	Number of publications	Percentage (%)	Citations	TC/P	Average TC/P/Y	Impact factor 2023
forest ecology and management	10	5.15	484	48.40	2.52	3.7
journal of ethnopharmacology	8	4.12	393	49.13	4.12	5.4
acta amazonica	5	2.58	19	3.80	0.42	0.8
electronic journal of environmental, agricultural and food chemistry	3	1.55	48	16.00	1.08	6.1
renewable energy	3	1.55	69	23.00	4.35	8.7
revista arvore	3	1.55	2	0.67	0.05	0.5
biochemical journal	2	1.03	326	163.00	3.98	4.1
Biotropica	2	1.03	124	62.00	2.55	2.1
comptes rendus hebdomadaires des seances de l'academie des sciences serie d	2	1.03	1	0.50	0.01	
foods and raw materials	2	1.03	2	1.00	0.20	2.0
international journal of ambient energy	2	1.03	7	3.50	0.44	3.63
journal of food agriculture & environment	2	1.03	5	2.50	0.16	
leather and footwear journal	2	1.03	4	2.00	0.40	0.21
petroleum and coal	2	1.03	4	2.00	0.29	5.6
revista cubana de plantas medicinales	2	1.03	3	1.50	0.09	
trees-structure and function	2	1.03	70	35.00	2.19	2.3
freshwater biology	1	0.52	263	263.00	11.43	2.7
cancer surveys	1	0.52	177	177.00	4.21	5.2
ecohydrology	1	0.52	152	152.00	16.89	2.6
canadian journal of forest research	1	0.52	139	139.00	6.62	2.2
antiviral research	1	0.52	136	136.00	6.48	7.6
landscape and urban planning	1	0.52	130	130.00	9.29	9.1
biomass conversion and biorefinery	1	0.52	6	6.00	6.00	4
veterinary parasitology	1	0.52	69	69.00	5.75	2.6
agricultural and forest meteorology	1	0.52	71	71.00	5.07	6.2
food and chemical toxicology	1	0.52	29	29.00	4.83	4.3
evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine	1	0.52	24	24.00	4.80	2.0
pharmaceutics	1	0.52	19	19.00	4.75	5.4
journal of the north american benthological society	1	0.52	82	82.00	4.56	2.35
biodiversity and conservation	1	0.52	72	72.00	4.24	3.4
bioenergy research	1	0.52	20	20.00	3.33	3.6
febs letters	1	0.52	93	93.00	3.32	3.5
environmental research	1	0.52	53	53.00	3.31	8.3
hydrobiologia	1	0.52	3	3.00	3.00	2.6

Most Active and Influential Sources

Among all the source publishing research on *Hura crepitans*, *Forest Ecology, and Management* was the most active, with 10 publications (5.15% of the total) and 484 citations, averaging 48.40 citations per publication and a yearly average of 2.52 (Table 2).

The *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* followed closely with 8 articles (4.12%) and 393 citations, averaging 49.13 citations per publication and a remarkable yearly rate of 4.12. In addition to important sources are *Acta Amazonica*, with 5 publications and 19 citations (3.80 citations per publication, 0.42 per

year), and the *Electronic Journal of Environmental, Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, which had 3 publications and 48 citations, averaging 16 citations per publication and 1.08 yearly. *Renewable Energy* also lit up through 3 publications and 69 citations (23 citations per publication, 4.35 per year). Several journals, despite offering few papers, have significant citation impacts. For instance, the *Biochemical Journal* has two articles that had a total of 326 citations, an average of a remarkable 163 citations per publication, and 3.98 annually. Similarly, *Biotropica* has two articles with 124 citations, an average of 62 citations per publication and 2.55 yearly. *Freshwater Biology* and *Cancer Surveys* each had one publication but had significant citation counts of 263 and 177, respectively, showing their main impact in the area. The collective impact of these publications is substantial, with 3934 citations. Each publication receives approximately 20.28 citations, indicating active scholarly engagement. The average annual citation rate per publication is 1.36.

Authors and their countries

The spatial distribution of knowledge using the total number of publications per country on *Hura crepitans* indicates 36 countries that contributed. Among them, only 8 were from Africa (Fig. 2). Based on the global geographical distribution, the research on this species is significantly concentrated in certain countries like Nigeria, which records a high number of publications between 25 and 91, followed by Brazil (17-24) and the United States (10 -16). The countries which have recorded the lowest (01) number of publications are Benin, Niger, Ethiopia and India.

The contribution of continents, regions, and countries in publications on *Hura crepitans* depicted that Western Africa, particularly Nigeria, dominates the diagram, indicating that this region contributes most significantly to research on *Hura crepitans* (Fig. 3). Following this, South America, with countries like Brazil, Peru, Venezuela, and Colombia, forms the second category of major contributors to research on *Hura crepitans*. Conversely, South Asia, specifically India, is shown as the region contributing the least.

To analyze the collaboration between authors, only 178 publications, representing 91.75%, were considered, and the remaining 8.25% were single authors' publications and therefore irrelevant for collaboration analysis. The collaborative publications were done by 683 authors with 1956 edges regardless of the number of publications that two authors did together, depicting a dense network of connections among authors and resulting in about 109 smaller networks (Fig. 4a). However, when one publication edge is removed (Fig. 4b), the network becomes significantly sparser, with only 123 edges among the same 683 nodes. This indicates that many collaborations were based on a single publication. When isolated nodes are eliminated from the collaboration network, leaving only authors with a minimum of two publications published together (Fig. 4c), only 75 nodes remain with 123 edges established in 18 clusters, including 5 clusters of collaboration between two authors. The largest and strongest cluster is centered on Trinel M. and formed by authors like Roumy V., Ruiz L., Samaille J., Rivière C., Sahpaz S., Bordage S., Dubuisson J., Hennebelle T., Le Lamer AC., Jullian V., Jacquemin D., Crossay E., Rolland C., Mejia K., Cabanillas BJ., Racaud-Sultan C., Fabre N., Owojuyigbe O.S., Larbie C., Firempong C.K., Komlaga G., and Emikpe B.O. Strong collaboration existed among the two authors' clusters between Ajiwe V.I.E. and Ogbu I.M.

Based on information on authors' countries available on 193 publications, only 43 publications resulted in collaboration between countries and were used to access collaborations between authors' countries. The initial network, regardless of the number of publications, revealed 38 edges between the 28 countries, placing at the center of the network United States with strong collaboration between Nigeria, South Africa, and Costa Rica even though the strongest collaboration was established between Peru and France (Fig. 5a). By investigating the network centered on the United States (Fig. 5b) and the network centered on Nigeria (Fig. 5c), it was revealed that the network centered on Nigeria had a greater number of collaborative countries (09) than the one

centered on the United States (08 countries). After countries with one edge were isolated and removed to focus on countries with at least two collaborative publications (Fig. 5d), only 14 countries remained with 11 edges. The largest and strongest network was centered around Nigeria, and it had the strongest collaboration with the United States and South Africa.

Publications' content analysis outcomes

The content analysis of publications on *Hura crepitans* was done utilizing the word clouds and the thematic maps built from publications' titles and abstracts, as well as an in-depth study of publications to point out key discoveries. While generating the word cloud, to avoid being misled by the search terms, *Hura crepitans* was eliminated from the word cloud output to focus on pertinent collections of words different from the main keyword. This enables visual representations of commonly occurring words to be shown.

Word clouds and thematic maps results

The content analysis *via* the thematic map offered a comprehensive view of thematic trends in *Hura crepitans* research and potential future fields of investigation by organizing the meaningful terms into four distinct areas: niche themes, motor themes, emerging or declining themes, and basic themes (Fig. 6).

By exploring these variables together, we acquire helpful data. The title word cloud shows phrases like "seed oil", "crepitans seed", "sandbox Hura", "tree species", and "chemical composition", indicating a broad interest in seed-related characteristics and the tree species.

This correlates with the large number of "seed oils" and "sandbox seed" in the driving themes of the thematic map, suggesting main studies focused on the seed composition of this plant species.

Fig. 1. Total number of publications and citations for research on *Hura crepitans*.

The abstracts word cloud gets more, showing words like "medicinal plants"; fatty acid", "tree species". It is associated well with the motor topics and signifies a focus on *Hura crepitans* ' potential for biofuel production (also suggested by "biodiesel production" in rising topics), "soil water", "Leaf bag". In addition,

terms like "antimicrobial activity" indicate towards growing interest in researching *Hura crepitans* for medical use. Finally, the presence of "tree species" in both word clouds, positioned as essential topics, shows a well-established focus on understand *Hura crepitans* in its ecological context.

Exploring the Potential Benefits of Hura crepitans: A Synthesis of Research Findings

Research on *Hura crepitans* has focused predominantly on the species seeds, as revealed in the word cloud and the thematic maps. *Hura crepitans*' seed and leaf extracts exhibited antimicrobial activity against various insects including *Plasmodium falciparum* parasite (Fernández-Caliènes *et al.*, 2011; Okeniyi *et al.*, 2018). The biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using aqueous extracts from *Hura crepitans* seeds further highlighted its potential in medical applications due to the antimicrobial activity exhibited by the synthesized nanoparticles (Jonathan *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, the seed oils of the species exhibit promising nutraceutical potential, containing essential minerals like magnesium, potassium, iron, and zinc while being free from harmful heavy metals such as nickel (Ajani *et al.*, 2019). These phytochemicals contribute to its utility in various industrial applications, particularly in the food and pharmaceutical sectors. It was found that *Hura crepitans*' seed oil (HCSO) supplementation in rats reduced pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, suggesting anti-inflammatory properties (Jonathan *et al.*, 2018). The presence of lectin, a protein in the seeds, with mitogenic activity (ability to stimulate cell division), specifically in human T lymphocytes, has been highlighted (Ajala *et al.*, 2023).

This lectin showed potency even at low concentrations and became more active with purification, suggesting potential applications in research or medicine. Leaf extracts' in vitro antioxidant activity was reported, highlighting the potential for countering oxidative damage (Kitadi *et al.*, 2024). However, authors observed potential anemia risks with long-term use of *Hura crepitans*' leaf extract in rats, emphasizing the need for further safety studies (Iannacone *et al.*, 2014). More recently, the mineral composition of *Hura crepitans*' leaves, bark, and seeds was analyzed (Kitadi *et al.*, 2024). Authors found that these organs contain minerals like iron, zinc, magnesium, and selenium, potentially beneficial for people with sickle cell disease (Kitadi *et al.*, 2024). While some toxicity of this plant species is

acknowledged (Iannacone *et al.*, 2014; Ezeh *et al.*, 2021; Ningrum *et al.*, 2024). *Hura crepitans*' extracts from various plant parts exhibit promising antimicrobial activity against large specimens of pathogens. Proper extraction techniques were important to manage *Hura crepitans*' known toxicity while harnessing its potential for therapeutic applications (Velazquez-González *et al.*, 2022). Authors examined how fermentation time affects the nutritional and chemical composition of ogiri, a condiment made from *Hura crepitans*' seeds (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2020). The study revealed significant changes during fermentation, with decreased carbohydrates, protein, and fiber content, while moisture content increased (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2020). Terpenoids were found throughout the process, while steroids were minimal. Overall, the study demonstrated the suitability of *Hura crepitans*' seeds for ogiri production, with fermentation influencing the final nutritional profile (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2020).

As it is useful for humans' health and food, researchers have also reported the importance of *Hura crepitans*' seeds for animals. Indeed, the effectiveness of the species' seeds against coccidiosis in lambs has been investigated, and the findings indicated that *Hura crepitans* Seed Oil (HCSO) exhibits anticoccidial properties, potentially offering a viable and natural alternative to conventional anticoccidial therapies for livestock (Velazquez-González *et al.*, 2022). The potential of *Hura crepitans*' seed meal (HCSM) as a feed supplement for sheep has been assessed, and analysis revealed a crude protein content of 251.1 g/kg and a dry matter content of 931.7 g/kg in HCSM (Velazquez-González *et al.*, 2022).

The study also showed promising digestibility, with the highest dry matter degradability (DMD) observed within the first 3 hours of incubation, showing a change rate of 41%. Additionally, *Hura crepitans*' seed meal provided essential amino acids, including glutamic acid (16.9%), arginine (13.0%), and aspartic acid (9.7%).

Fig. 2. Global geographical distribution of publications on *Hura crepitans* based on authors' countries.

These findings suggest that HCSM could be a valuable source of nutrients for ruminant animals, with a gradual energy utilization reaching a maximum of 14.6% after 72 hours post-incubation (Escalera-Valente *et al.*, 2022).

These studies highlight the significant ethnopharmacological and medicinal potential of *Hura crepitans*' organs for both humans and animals. Additionally, research on biodiesel production from the seeds of *Hura crepitans* shows promise. The oil extracted from the seeds has been successfully converted into biodiesel through transesterification (Otoikhian *et al.*, 2016; Sidohoude *et al.*, 2019; Escalera-Valente *et al.*, 2022), indicating favorable fuel properties and potential as a sustainable feedstock. Moreover, the development of recyclable catalysts from seed pods for biodiesel production has been investigated (Ogbu *et al.*, 2018). This method offers a sustainable and cost-effective solution by utilizing waste products and achieving high catalytic activity (up to 94.81% ester conversion) with good reusability. A neural network model was developed to predict oil yield during solvent-based extraction from *Hura crepitans* seeds (Ajala *et al.*, 2023). The potential of *Hura crepitans* seed oil (HCSO) as a sustainable raw material for waterborne alkyd resins has also been explored. Research suggests that HCSO

and other plant-based oils could be a viable alternative to petroleum-derived materials in various industrial applications (Issac *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, waste sandbox shells as a green catalyst for biodiesel production has been examined, promoting resource efficiency (Yeung *et al.*, 2018).

In the cosmetics industry, the use of *Hura crepitans* seed oil (HCSO) in developing emollient creams was studied (Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). They extracted HCSO *via* solvent extraction and characterized it using standard methods. The researchers prepared aluminum and magnesium soaps from palm kernel oil sodium soap through the precipitation method to serve as thickeners and emulsifiers in the cream formulation, alongside shea butter and an aqueous extract of turmeric, demonstrating HCSO's potential for cosmetic applications.

In the pulp and paper industry, the suitability of *Hura crepitans* leaves as an alternative raw material was investigated. The analysis revealed favorable properties, including high lignin and cellulose content, low solubility in sodium hydroxide solution, and appropriate fiber lengths for papermaking, suggesting that *Hura crepitans* leaves have the potential for sustainable pulp and paper production (Isaac *et al.*, 2022).

Discussion

Despite multiple advantages related to sandbox trees, research on this species from 1909 to 2024 remains limited, particularly in the wood industry or ethnobotany fields. Integrating ethnopharmacology studies with bibliometric analyses could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the plant's historical uses and research trends. For example, studies such as those by Ritter *et al.* (2015) and Yeung *et al.* (2018) highlighted the importance of ethnopharmacological knowledge in understanding the full scope of *Hura crepitans*' applications.

Fig. 3. Contribution of continents, regions, and countries in publications on *Hura crepitans*.

While a noticeable increase in *Hura crepitans* research is observed post-2000, potentially driven by growing interest in its pharmacological applications, this surge requires a nuanced interpretation. While ecological and pharmacological potentials are contributing factors in botanical research trends (Saraiva *et al.*, 2019), it might overlook other important influences. For instance, the increased accessibility of digital databases and online publishing platforms in the late 20th and early 21st centuries could have played a role in the observed trend. Furthermore, attributing research peaks solely to scientific breakthroughs or policy shifts (Moyer *et al.*, 2017), neglects the potential impact of evolving societal interests and funding priorities. A more comprehensive analysis should consider the influence of funding trends, technological advancements, and

evolving research priorities within specific disciplines. For example, the rise of interdisciplinary fields like ethnopharmacology (Jorim *et al.*, 2012; Ningthoujam *et al.*, 2012; Leonti and Casu, 2013) could be a significant driver of increased research on traditionally used plants like *Hura crepitans*.

The significance of English in *Hura crepitans* publications highlights a crucial concern in scientific communication: the language obstacle. Despite English emerging as the universal language of science, this gives rise to inherent accessibility obstacles for researchers in non-English speaking areas (Fleury and Heredia, 2023). This prevalence is underscored in studies by some authors which point out the dominant impact of English in scientific publishing, particularly in disciplines such as computer science (Cheriguene *et al.*, 2020).

This linguistic bias not only limits the dissemination of knowledge but can also hinder the participation and recognition of researchers from diverse linguistic backgrounds (Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020). This is particularly relevant for *Hura crepitans*' research, where valuable traditional knowledge held within local communities might not be readily accessible in English-language publications.

Furthermore, as suggested, promoting multilingualism in scientific communication, such as providing translations of abstracts or key findings, could significantly broaden the reach and impact of research, fostering greater inclusivity and knowledge exchange. This is particularly crucial for research on species like *Hura crepitans*, which has significant cultural and ecological importance in various regions worldwide. Key journals such as *Forest Ecology and Management* and the *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* have been major channels for disseminating research on *Hura crepitans*. However, a geographical analysis reveals that research efforts are heavily concentrated in regions like Nigeria and Brazil. This focus aligns with the plant's introduction to Nigeria and the prevalence of traditional ethnomedical knowledge in these areas.

Fig. 4. Social networks of collaboration between authors regardless of the number of publications published together (a), with only one publication edge removed (b), with a minimum of two publications published together (c).

This regional emphasis, while important, risks overlooking the potential diversity of *Hura crepitans* across its entire range and the valuable insights that can be gained from local knowledge. For instance, the diverse traditional uses and economic value of *Ricinodendron heudelotii* in Benin demonstrate the importance of local knowledge in understanding plant resources (Akpovo *et al.*, 2023) highlights the diverse traditional uses and economic value of *Ricinodendron heudelotii* in Benin, demonstrating the importance of local knowledge in understanding plant resources. Similar specific researches explore the potential of *Hura crepitans*' seed oil for biodiesel production in Benin, showcasing the need to investigate region-specific applications (Montcho, 2016; Sidohoude *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, research (Dicko *et al.*, 2019) emphasizes the influence of ethnic groups on the utilization and knowledge of plant species like *Lophira lanceolata* in Benin. This underscores the importance of considering socio-cultural factors when studying the distribution and use of *Hura crepitans* across its range. A broader geographical perspective

in *Hura crepitans*' research, particularly within understudied African regions, will not only enhance our understanding of its biology and ecology but also contribute to more effective and context-specific conservation and resource management strategies. The collaborative analysis between the author and between countries reveals a centralized structure, with the United States and Nigeria emerging as key collaborative hubs, showing the importance of these countries in advancing research on this species. Research on *Hura crepitans* is still in its early stages, particularly when compared to other regions like Africa, where research on Gum Arabic has been more extensive (Honorio Coronado *et al.*, 2023). Further, the ethnobotanical survey on medicinal plants in Nigeria's Ughelli North Local Government Area highlights the traditional use of *Hura crepitans* for various ailments (Treasure *et al.*, 2020), suggesting its potential in the realm of traditional medicine (Oraegbunam *et al.*, 2020). While pharmacological and botanical studies provide a crucial foundation for understanding *Hura crepitans*, they represent only a

research. Current studies predominantly focused on the plant's phytochemistry and bioactivity, exploring its potential applications in medicine and sustainable industries. For instance, investigations into *Hura crepitans*' secondary metabolites have revealed promising antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, particularly in its leaves, seeds, and bark. Furthermore, researchers have begun exploring its potential for sustainable applications, such as biodiesel production from its seed oil and its use in pulp and paper production. However, other crucial research areas remain underexplored. Despite its reported toxicity, comprehensive safety assessments of *Hura crepitans* are limited, hindering its

responsible utilization. Further investigation into its toxicological profile is crucial to ensure safe handling and application. The wood production potential of *Hura crepitans* has been explored, but findings suggest limitations for commercial timber production due to insufficient regeneration (Stephen *et al.*, 1995).

This highlights the need for research into sustainable cultivation practices and conservation strategies to ensure the long-term availability of *Hura crepitans* as a valuable resource. This highlights the need for research into sustainable cultivation practices and conservation strategies to ensure the long-term availability of *Hura crepitans* as a valuable resource.

Fig. 6. Word cloud outcome of the 50 meaningful groups of words from the publications' titles (up left), publications' abstracts (upright), and their respective thematic map.

Beyond its practical applications, understanding *Hura crepitans*' ecological role requires further investigation. While studies have shed light on its unique seed dispersal mechanisms and pollination strategies (Tobias *et al.*, 2019; Ribera *et al.*, 2020), broader ecological research remains limited, particularly regarding its interactions with other species and its role in ecosystem dynamics. The potential of *Hura crepitans* seed shells in water treatment through activated carbon production has

been highlighted (Nsi *et al.*, 2016), emphasizing the value of exploring diverse applications.

A comparative approach, contrasting *Hura crepitans* with related Euphorbiaceae species, could provide valuable insights into its unique characteristics and potential. This approach could encompass various aspects, from phytochemical profiles and bioactivities to ecological interactions and evolutionary adaptations.

Research on *Hura crepitans* is progressing; however, a strategic shift in focus is needed to address critical knowledge gaps. Prioritizing research on its toxicology, sustainable cultivation, ecological interactions, and comparative analysis will provide a more comprehensive understanding of this fascinating and potentially valuable species. This aligns with the principles of academic publishing, which encourages a balanced and comprehensive exploration of research topics to advance scientific knowledge effectively (Habib *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

Hura crepitans, also called sandbox trees, have been of increasing scientific attention in recent years due to the increased understanding of environmental difficulties and traditional medical values for such species. Although most studies are written in English, future studies should involve multiple languages to improve scientific knowledge. *Hura crepitans* is native to the American continent; this species is not studied there alone.

In Western Africa, notably Nigeria, when species is introduced, it can be noticed that this is one of its key research fields, showing that it has gotten strongly integrated into local activities and ecosystems. South America is second among the world's top countries contributing to research on *Hura crepitans*. This suggests that apart from being naturally prevalent in particular places and having a presence in corresponding traditional medical applications, the same case cannot be affirmed for other plants located elsewhere internationally since their local medicinal use could vary per plant species. Despite the diversity of publications found on this species, additional research is necessary to appreciate its potential fully. It is vital to conduct extensive toxicological investigations, sustainable farming practices, and ecological interactions beyond the natural habitat of this plant to ensure its safe usage in possible applications. In addition, it would be good to examine how adaptable this species is, its ecological connection, and its uses in other African countries into which it has been introduced.

Author contributions

Yevide SIA:

Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Yebadokpo SK: Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft.

Gbesso GHF: Conceptualization, Resources, Data curation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. All authors finalized the format and commented on the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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